

METRO AND ITS UNOPENED EDGES**Abdurahmonov Adxamjon***Senior lecturer, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute***Hatamova Durdona***Senior lecturer, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute***Jumanazarov Azamat***Student, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute***Dadaxanov Olimjon***Student, Namangan Engineering - Construction Institute*

Abstract: This article provides information about the importance of subways in the world and in our republic.

Key words: metro, traffic, high-speed trains, underground transport systems.

In our modern world, the word "traffic" refers to traffic jams, and at the same time, it encourages us to flee to the fast subway. After all, you will not face any traffic jams and excessive waiting there. Everything will be based on your plan. At the moment, traffic in our country is satisfactory, we will see in 5-10 years, will there be traffic jams like in Europe? Then it becomes common for the cars to stay in their place for an hour without moving. Therefore, the value of the metro will increase, the demand for it will increase, passengers will start moving towards the metro twice as many as before.

Most of us know about the emergence of train, automobile, steamship. But what about the subway? What do you know about the subway? When and where was it discovered, who invented it? Like steam engines, the inventor of the subway is from that old England. So, Charles Pearson from London "threw his hat to the sky" from this idea that came to his clever mind in 1846. He was not in a hurry at first. After thinking everything through, he got the job done - he shot the architectural

drawings that needed to be drawn and went to the Royal Commission on Straight Railways. Can you imagine that this is happening almost two centuries ago - in 1846! At that time, he had neither a bus nor a car. Thus, Pearson's project was successful in the commission, and 14 years later - in 1860, the construction of the subway began in London. At that time, the first tunnel was dug for the famous Euston Square. The name of the construction company that carried out the excavation work was "Metropolitan". Now you must have noticed how the word "metro" appeared and where it came from! Thus, the opening of the world's first metro took place in 1863. The line had 7 stations, and its length was only 3.5 km. This route was covered in 33 minutes. The cars were lit by gas. The number of carriages in one train was 4, which was pulled by a locomotive, as a result of which the subway was filled with steam and smoke. It was only in 1890 that the subway was electrified, and for the first time, the prince of the country walked in it. In fact, a person felt much better in the subway, which was smoke-free and much quieter than before.

With almost daily construction going on, the London Underground has been improving year by year. The first ring road appeared as early as 1868, and in 1908 Albert Stanley found another way to make passengers more comfortable: a subway route suggested to draw the schemes and hang them on the stations.

The new invention of mankind quickly spread to other countries of the world. For example, the United States, which was England's "brother" at that time, took the subway system to its own country in 1872 and built it in New York. In 1896, the metro entered Eastern Europe as well - this time it was built in Budapest. Two years later, Paris, and in 1900, residents of Berlin saw the new type of transport with their own eyes. You also got acquainted with the history of the emergence of the metro. Now we will tell a detailed story about the most beautiful and unusual metro in the world - the Paris metro. The Paris metro is probably the busiest metro not only in Europe, but also in the world. Here, some stations are only 500 meters apart. The entrance to the subway

reminiscent of a secret door leading to an underground passage. Very narrow and small, built at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century and has not been changed until now. As soon as you enter, a strange feeling overtakes you: you immediately feel the mysterious, miniature form of the stations.

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